

Zhou --, 61 years old, male

Chief complaint: The patient has had type 2 diabetes for 18 years. The left heel has been ulcerated for 4 months

History of present illness: The patient complained of polydipsia, polyuria, polyphagia and weight loss under no obvious predisposing causes 18 years ago, but was free of blurred vision, numbness of limbs, nausea, vomiting, palpitation, tremor, dizziness and weakness. He was diagnosed as type 2 diabetes in a local hospital based on elevated blood glucose. Since then, he started to reduce blood glucose by using insulin, but the blood glucose level was not tested regularly. His left heel was ulcerated under no obvious predisposing causes 4 months ago. The ulceration was improved by surgery in a local hospital, but relapsed a month ago. He came to our hospital for further treatment.

Past medical history: The patient was diagnosed as stage 5 chronic kidney disease (CKD) 4 years ago. Since then, he started to receive maintenance hemodialysis every Monday and Friday.

No abnormalities were found in personal history and family history.

Specialized physical examination: A 1.5cm*1cm black scab was observed on the left heel. The scab has explicit boundaries, but was not red and swollen. Pressing the scab created a pain, but no obvious pus effused. The left lower extremity ached. No apparent abnormalities were found in the active and passive motion of the left ankle and all joints of the left foot.